

ON THE COMPOSITION OF SILVER CITRATE

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In previous communications (Dey, *Compt. rend. Acad. Sci., U.S.S.R.*, 1947, 59, 1047; *J. Coll. Sci.*, 1948, 3, 473) the formation of a soluble complex between silver and citrate ions has been described. When a soluble citrate is added to a silver nitrate solution, a white curdy precipitate is obtained, which dissolves in excess of citrate, forming the argentocitrate complex (Mukherji and Dey, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 12, 501; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1955, 148, 94). The composition of the precipitated silver citrate seems to have remained uninvestigated and it is considered worthwhile to investigate its composition. A similar precipitate is also formed by adding sodium, potassium or ammonium hydroxide solution to the colorless solution obtained by dissolving silver citrate in an excess of citric acid solution. In this note we have found the composition of the white curdy precipitate to be Ag_3Cit in every case.

Procedure.—Standard solutions of silver nitrate, sodium citrate, citric acid and sodium, ammonium and potassium hydroxides were prepared using BDH-Analar reagents and dissolving in double-distilled water. All the solutions were standardised by the usual methods.

In the first set of experiments 25 c.c. of 0.125 *M* silver nitrate was taken and 1 *M* solution of sodium dihydrogen citrate was added dropwise till precipitation was complete. The precipitate was kept overnight, filtered in a sintered glass crucible and was thoroughly washed with water. The precipitate was dried in an air-oven at 100-110°, and then analysed for its silver content which was found to be 62.39% (Ag calc. for Ag_3Cit : 63.13%).

In a second set of experiments equal volumes of 0.125 *M* silver nitrate and 1 *M* citric acid were mixed and to the mixture varying amounts of 2 *M* sodium, potassium or ammonium hydroxide were added. The precipitates obtained were washed and analysed after drying. In every case, the composition was found to be Ag_3Cit .

It is thus concluded that the precipitate in all cases is Ag_3Cit , i.e., silver replaces carboxylic hydrogen in citric acid to produce the insoluble citrate, and that the hydroxylic hydrogens are not involved in the formation of precipitated silver citrate. It is also evident that the soluble argentocitrate is unstable in presence of alkali and is decomposed to silver citrate on the addition of hydroxyl ions. Further work on complex citrates is in progress.

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